

Distribution of Molluscan fauna in *Coringa Estuarine* Mangroves, South East Coast of India

R. Rajendar Kumar

Marine Biology Regional Centre, Zoological Survey of India, Chennai-28

*Email: rrajendarkumarzsi@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study was conducted in Coringa mangrove rehabilitation area on September 2014. The objective of the present study was to evaluate the diversity of Gastropods and Bivalves based on the different level of vegetation age of mangrove. During the present survey, 11 species of molluscs were recorded. Among them 8 of gastropods, viz. *Telescopium telescopium* Linnaeus (1758), *Cerithidea cingulata* Gmelin 1791, and *Fusinus colus* (Linnaeus, 1758) 4 species of bivalves namely, *Andara granosa*, *Macra violaceae* Gmelin, 1791 *Gastrana polygona* (Gmelin, 1791), and *Anapella cycladea* (Lamarck, 1818) were observed. Till now, no studies have been taken up so far in these aspects. So, the present study has been taken up to provide some basic information of the mollusca fauna of the Coringa mangrove.

Key words: Mangrove, Gastropods, Bivalves.

INTRODUCTION

The study area is the fertile estuarine ecosystem on the east coast of India, the Godavari estuarine ecosystem, consisting of Kakinada Bay and the surrounding mangrove vegetation. The river Godavari is the second largest river in India (1530 Km). The drainage area is about 2,90,400 km². The normal run off from the Godavari is estimated at 4,60,316 million cusec. Meters (Govt. of India Report, 1987). The Kakinada Bay lies between 82°14' E and 82°22' E longitudes and 16°05' N and 17°0 N latitudes has an area of 132 km². (Rama Sarma, 1965). The Kakinada Bay acts as the main reservoir for the riverine discharge from Godavari's distributaries. Annual flooding of the rivers during monsoon period is a characteristic feature of many tropical rivers. On account of this the estuaries

near the river mouths experience extreme variations in physico-chemical parameters and biological aspects. In India the marine molluscs are recorded from the diverse habitats. They occur in different habitats such as mangroves, coral reef, rocky coasts, sandy beaches, sea grass beds and also at greater depth in the sea. They are more diverse and abundant in the rocky intertidal zone along the coast. Sandy stones, intertidal flats, mangrove areas [1]. Mangroves are one of the biologically diverse ecosystems in the world, rich in organic matter and nutrients and support very large biomass of flora and fauna [2]. Edible species of oysters, mussels, cockles, and gastropods are collected extensively for local consumption. Mangrove roots and lower parts of trunks provide substrate for oysters and mussels. Because these animals are filter feeders, they are confined to microhabitats below mean high water and are usually only abundant in areas adjacent to open water.

How to Site This Article:

R. Rajendar Kumar (2016). Distribution of Molluscan fauna in *Coringa Estuarine* Mangroves, South East Coast of India. *Biolife*, 4(2), pp 261-.
doi:10.17812/blj.2016.428

Published online: 17 April 2016

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area:

River Godavari bifurcates towards its lower reaches, and one of the branches, the Gautami Godavari, joins the Bay of Bengal at Bhairavapalem Kakinada bay is situated north of Gautami Godavari and is connected to

it by distributaries mainly Gaderu and Coringa. The Kakinada Bay lies between 82014' E and 82022'E longitudes and 160.5' N and 170 N latitudes has an area of 132 km². (Rama Sarma, 1965). Bhairavapalem is also the southern limit of the Bay-Mangrove complex that covers a total area of ~350 km². An important feature of this region is the location of Coringa Wildlife Sanctuary (250 km²) with high grown mangroves. The long and often branching mangrove creeks, where considerable lateral trapping of water occurs, serve as an excellent habitat and nursery for a wide range of invertebrate species and fish.

Survey of the Coringa mangrove conducted during the year 2014-2015. There was altogether 15 specimens collected from Coringa mangrove area. Mollusca shells were hand picked randomly from the exposed areas using qualitative and direct sampling methods. The collections are kept in dried form while some were preserved in 4% formaldehyde solution. All the samples collected were deposited in the Marine Biology Regional Centre, Zoological Survey of India, Chennai, and Tamilnadu. Screening of the collected material was carried out with stereo microscopes to assort it into species or higher taxonomic categories. After morphological analysis, all the shells collected, either death or alive were studied and identified using

relevant literatures and registered. The classification followed is that of Vaught [6].

RESULTS

In the present study, 15 species of molluscs were recorded in the Coringa mangrove, which includes 10 species of gastropods and 5 species of bivalves. The gastropods have a significant ecological role to play in the mangrove ecosystems, also rocky habitats is suitable especially for gastropods. However very little information is available on the gastropod biodiversity of mangroves. Hence it is necessary to document the biodiversity of the group of threatened ecosystems. There is an urgent need for conservation and sustainable utilization of molluscan species.

Acknowledgment

The author is grateful to director, Zoological survey of India and also to Officer-in charge, MBRC, ZSI, Chennai for providing necessary facilities. The author wishes to express deep sense of gratitude to Dr. G. Shivaleela, Scientist "C", MBRC, Chennai for encouragement and support.

Figure-1. Coringa mangrove, Andhra Pradesh State, India.

Table-1. The comprehensive list of molluscs found in the Coringa mangrove areas.

GASTROPODA	
Species	Authority
<i>Telescopium telescopium</i>	(Linnaeus, 1758)
<i>Cerithidea alata</i>	Philippi, 1847
<i>Cerithidea cingulata</i>	Gmelin, 1791
<i>Nerita polita</i>	Linnaeus, 1758
<i>Nerita undulata</i>	Gmelin, 1791
<i>Littoraria undulata</i>	Gray, 1839Philippi,
<i>Nassarius olivaceus</i>	Bruguiere, 1789
<i>Rhinoclavis aspera</i>	Linnaeus, 1758
<i>Fusinus colus</i>	(Linnaeus ,1758)
<i>Nassanus stolatus</i> (Gmelin, 1791)	(Gmelin, 1791)
BIVALVES	
<i>Anapella cycladea</i>	(Lamarck, 1818)
<i>Anadara granosa</i>	(Linnaeus, 1758)
<i>Mactra violaceae</i>	Gmelin, 1791
<i>Gastrana polygona</i>	Gmelin, 1791)
<i>Meretrix meretrix</i>	(Linnaeus, 1758)
<i>Gafrarium pectinatum</i>	(Lirulaeus, 1758)
<i>Solen brevis</i>	Gray, 1842
<i>Bactronophorus thoracites</i>	Gould, 1856
<i>Bankia bipennata</i>	Turton, 1819
<i>Bankia nordi</i>	Moll and Roch, 1931
<i>Bankia carinata</i>	Gray, 1827
<i>Bankia campanellata</i>	Moll and Roch, 1931

Mactra violaceae
(Gmelin, 1791)

Gastrana polygona
(Gmelin, 1791)

Anadara granosa
{Linnaeus, 1758)

Anapella cycladea
(Lamarck, 1818)

Conflict of Interests

Authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

References

- [1]. Alfred J. B., Varshney R. K., Ghosh A. K. (eds) 1997 An assessment manual for faunal biodiversity in South Asia. SACEP/NORAD Publication Series on Biodiversity in South Asia No 1, 181pp.
- [2]. Boominathan, M., Chandran, M.D.S., Ramachandra, T.V., (2008). Economic Valuation of Bivalves in the Aghanashini Estuary, West Coast, Karnataka. ENVIS Technical Report: 30. Centre for Ecological Sciences, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, India
- [3]. Chakravarty M.S. and Joseph Uday Ranjan T., (2014). A Check List of Malacofauna from The Nuvvalarevu Backwaters of Srikakulam District, Andhra Pradesh, India. International Journal of Research in Marine Sciences 3(1): 11-15.
- [4]. Dey, A., 2006, *Handbook on mangrove associate molluscs of Sundarbans*. Zoological Survey of India, Kolkata, pp 96
- [5]. Das. A.K. & Roy, M.K.D., (1989). A general account of the mangrove fauna of Andaman and Nicobar islands. Conservation area series, Zoological survey of India 4: 1-73.
- [6]. Ganapati, P.N. and Rao, M.V.L. 1959. Incidence of marine borers in the mangrove of Godavari estuary. Current Science, 28(8): 332.

Fusinus colus
(Linnaeus ,1758)

Telescopium telescopium
(Linnaeus, 1758)

Cerithidea cingulata
Gmelin, 1791

Nerita undulata Gmelin,
1791

- [7]. Hogarth P. J., 2001 Mangrove ecosystems. pp. 853-870. In: Encyclopaedia of Biodiversity. Vol. 3. Academic Press.
- [8]. Kathiresan K., Bingham B. L., 2001 Biology of mangroves and mangroves ecosystems. *Adv Mar Biol* 40:84–251.
- [9]. Kesavan, K., Palpandi, C. and Shanmugam, A. 2009. A checklist of malacofauna of the Vellar estuarine mangroves, India. *Journal of Threatened Taxa*, 1(7): 382-384.
- [10]. Mahapatra, A., 2001, *Molluscan fauna of Godavari estuary: Fauna of Godavari, Estuarine Ecosystem series*, 4:55-82. Zoological Survey of India.
- [11]. Pawar R. Prabhakar, 2012. Molluscan Diversity in Mangrove Ecosystem of Uran (Raigad), Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra, West coast of India. *Bull. Environ. Pharmacol. Life Sci.* Vol. 1(6) 55-59.
- [12]. Ramakrishna and A. Dey. Annotated checklist of Indian Marine Molluscs (Cephalopoda, Bivalve and Scaphopoda) Part-1. *Rec.Zool.Surv.India, Occ. Paper no.*, 320:1-357. (Published by the Director, Zool.Surv.India, and Kolkata).
- [13]. Radhakrishna, Y. and Janakiram K., (1975). The mangrove molluscs of Godavari and Krishna estuaries. In: Natarajan, R. (Ed.), *Recent Researches in Estuarine Biology*, 20-24 Jan 1972. Porto Novo. Hindustan Publishing Corporation, Delhi, India, 177-184.
- [14]. Vaught, K.C, 1989, *A classification of the living Mollusca* ed. (R.T. Abbott and K.J.Boss) American Malacologist, U.S.A, pp 189.

DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7317717>

Received: 4 April 2016;

Accepted; 19 May 2016;

Available online : 3 June 2016
